

1 **Synthetic lethal relationship between Ezh2 and Parp1 in cancer cells.**

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 By measuring cell death following loss of gene function using whole transcriptome technologies we
8 observed a strong, synthetic lethal relationship between the Poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase *Parp1* and the
9 H3K27 methyltransferase *Ezh2*. Parp1 chemotherapeutic regimens may benefit from adjunctive Ezh2
10 inhibition.

11 Citations

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1. Meng, Q., Shen, J., Ren, Y., Liu, Q., Wang, R., Li, Q., Jiang, W., Wang, Q., Zhang, Y., Trinidad, J.C. and Lu, X., 2024. EZH2 directly methylates PARP1 and regulates its activity in cancer. *Science Advances*, 10(48), p.eadl2804.